

Generative AI Explainer

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The purpose of this zine is to provide explanations of the technical terms used in discussions of generative AI, to help strip back some of the mystique and hyped claims around these technologies. I designed it using Canva, incorporating public domain vintage prints of speculative automated technologies and images from Canva of current digital hardware. I put the definitions together using research I conducted with no 'help' from GenAI services.

- **artificial intelligence (AI):** A term used to describe software that supposedly can mimic or surpass human intelligence in performing at least one specific task (also referred to as ‘narrow AI’). The term Artificial General Intelligence (AGI) or ‘General AI’ refers to hypothetical software that can independently perform an unlimited variety of tasks in ways that match or exceed human cognitive abilities. It is often suggested by AI boosters that AGI is ‘nearly here’, but as yet there is no indication that it will be achieved in the near future, if at all.
- **AI agent:** A software program designed to autonomously perform complex tasks and decision-making without constant human oversight by establishing workflows. Sometimes also referred to as LLM agents as LLMs are core to their functioning.
- **AI model:** A statistical computer program that applies algorithms to process text, images and audio in massive datasets to identify patterns and conduct automated decision-making and predictions.
- **AI stack:** The infrastructure required to create and deploy AI services and applications, including software such as computer models, programs, platforms and security systems, the datasets used by the programs and hardware such as computer chips, servers, cables and data centres.
- **AI system:** Combines several models of different sizes and capabilities together with a chat interface, content processing, web access and application integration.
- **algorithm:** A set of instructions used in computer programming, designed to accomplish a specific task (often compared to recipes).
- **central processing unit (CPU):** The primary functional component of a computer, constituted of an assemblage of electronic circuitry that run computers’ operating systems and applications.

data centre

data servers inside a data centre

- **chatbot:** The public interface of an LLM that responds to queries or prompts by mimicking a human conversational style.
- **computational resources ('compute'):** The technical requirements for developing and deploying AI systems, including specialised computer chips and other hardware, software and infrastructure.
- **data:** The content that is used by LLMs and IGMs, including text, numbers, audio and visual materials.
- **data centre:** A building supporting computing and data storage and processing systems, built from concrete, steel and aluminium. These buildings incorporate thousands of data server racks and storage devices for data processing, networking connectivity hardware such as switches, routers and fibre-optic cables, power systems, cooling systems, backup power sources such as generators, and physical security systems such as cameras and secure perimeters. Data centres vary in size and scale. Enterprise data centres are used mainly by a company's employees and clients while many companies rent space in shared data centres. Edge data centres are small-scale facilities located close to the end user. Hyperscale data centres are massive and are typically owned by large cloud service and AI companies.
- **data server:** A software application used to store and manage large volumes of data and provide mechanisms for users to scrape, retrieve, store or manipulate data.
- **data work:** The human labour required to program the models, collect, scrape, curate, check, clean, standardise and label the data that are fed into the models, and to monitor and fine-tune the software. Some people are paid to provide tech corporations to collect data, such as videos of locations they inhabit or their own phone calls or texts. Also often referred to as **digital labour**.

close up of data servers

fibre-optic cables

- **deep learning:** A type of automated machine learning using massive unstructured datasets (for example, images, audio and text) and large-scale computational resources to improve AI models' capabilities. Deep learning algorithms adjust the strength of various connections between neurons to improve the models' performance. Typically used for computer vision, image recognition, converting speech to text and natural language processing.
- **discriminative AI:** Machine learning software that classifies or labels input data for purposes such as object recognition (for example, distinguishing between a cat or a dog in images in a dataset), medical diagnosis, facial recognition or spam detection.
- **e-waste (electronic waste):** The materials used in computing system hardware and digital devices that are discarded when no longer required.
- **generative AI:** Software involving LLMs and IGMs which draw on massive datasets to make calculations about how words, computer code, audio or visual content should be formulated in response to user queries or prompts. This software typically involves forms of automated decision-making, machine learning, computer vision, speech recognition, data classification and prediction based on statistical inference and algorithmic processing. LLMs predict the next word or set of characters ('token') in a sequence, drawing on billions of different tokens, to create coherent responses to queries or prompts. IGMs process visual patterns in similar ways, drawing on images that have been described and tagged using natural language.

central processing unit (computer chip)

e-waste

- **generative pretrained transformer (GPT) model:** Software that creates new data by turning words, images and sounds into numerical formats.
- **ghost workers:** The human workers performing data work that are often invisible and unacknowledged by tech companies.
- **graphics processing unit (GPU):** A specialised electronic circuit designed to speed computer graphics and image processing on devices such as video cards, system boards and personal computers by undertaking parallel processing (doing many small tasks at once). Nvidia makes many of the GPUs used in generative AI technologies.
- **hallucination:** A term often used to describe the inaccuracies in the content made by generative AI software.
- **image generator model (IGM):** An AI model that produces new visual content in responses to natural language prompts or text descriptions by drawing on massive databases. It uses statistical analysis and machine learning to identify and duplicate patterns within the photographs, artwork and illustrations that have been included in the databases to generate a synthetic image. Examples are DALL-E, Midjourney and Stable Diffusion.
- **large language model (LLM):** An AI model that uses natural language processing to generate outputs that mimic human speech in response to users' prompts. LLMs are made accessible for public use through interfaces ('chatbots') such as ChatGPT (OpenAI), DeepSeek, Copilot (Microsoft), Claude (Anthropic), Grok (xAI), Llama (Meta) and Gemini (Google).
- **machine learning:** Computing systems that are conditioned to identify patterns and relationships in structured large datasets without requiring explicit programming for every step, enabling them to make predictions or decisions based on these patterns and relationships.

- **microchip:** A tiny piece of semiconductor material (usually made of silicon) that contains complex miniature electronic circuits. Also called a chip, a computer chip or an integrated circuit.
- **natural language:** The spoken or written words used by humans to communicate with each other, as distinct from programming language, which is a structured set of commands used by humans to create instructions for computers (software) to execute programs (for example, Python and JavaScript).
- **natural language processing:** A set of methods that make human language accessible and ready to be processed by computing. Examples of natural language processing include automated translation and text classification tools.
- **neural networks:** Networks of neurons, comprised of several input layers and an output layer.
- **neurons:** Layers of interconnected information-processing units.
- **predictive AI:** Computer systems involving statistical analysis and machine learning to identify patterns in historical data to estimate or anticipate future events or trends (for example, weather and economic forecasting and early disease detection models).
- **programming:** The process by which people design, write, test and maintain step-by-step instructions (code) for computer programs and systems, using programming language.
- **stochastic:** A statistical term meaning having a random probability distribution or pattern that can be analysed but not precisely predicted.

- **tensor processing unit (TPU):** A type of integrated circuit computer chip that has been customised to accelerate machine learning workloads. Often used for natural language processing, computer vision and recommendation systems.
- **token:** A tiny unit of data required for training AI models and for processing data once models are deployed. Digital tokens are generated through the computing process of tokenisation, which breaks down text, images or audio into smaller units (words, parts of words, punctuation, spaces or characters, audio or video segments). Each token is assigned a unique numerical identifier by the software. Prompts given to the model are translated into a series of input tokens, which the model then processes by drawing on the datasets to which it has access, generates its response as tokens and then translates these tokens into the expected formats.
- **transformer:** A specific neural network architecture that helps an AI model to focus on the most relevant parts of the input data when processing information.

transmission towers provide
electricity to data centres

Tab. III.

